

IMPACT OF SHOT PEENING ON THE FATIGUE STRENGTH OF ARC-WELDED ADVANCED HIGH STRENGTH STEEL ASSEMBLIES

A. Nabara^{1,2}, C. Mareau¹, F. Morel¹, M. R. Chini², R. Munier³, P. Kusakin & M. L. Facchinetti⁴

The present work aims at investigating the effect of shot peening on the fatigue behaviour of welded joints made of advanced high strength steel with a tensile strength of 600 MPa. Uniaxial fatigue tests were conducted on double lap joint specimens with both as-welded and shot-peened conditions at two loading ratios of 0.1 and -1. These tests were completed by X-ray diffraction analyses and roughness measurements. The fatigue test results indicate that shot peening improves the fatigue strength of welded specimens, especially at $R = -1$. The beneficial effect at $R = 0.1$ is reduced because of the redistribution of the residual stresses induced by cyclic plasticity. The effects of residual stresses, work hardening and surface roughness on the fatigue strength were estimated separately by comparing the results obtained for heat-treated and preloaded specimens. According to the results, the generation of compressive residual stress by shot peening is the major factor controlling the fatigue strength of lap joints. The effects of work hardening and surface roughness are negligible.

Keywords: Fatigue of welded joints, shot peening, residual stresses, advanced high strength steel

INTRODUCTION

Environmental constraints and fuel prices are encouraging industry to lighten the mechanical structure of vehicles. A promising solution consists of reducing the thickness of components by using Advanced High Strength Steels (AHSS). In the automotive industry, AHSS are possible candidates for chassis components, which are assembled by Gas Metal Arc Welding (GMAW). However, the presence of welds can be an issue for the fatigue strength of AHSS components. Indeed, studies have shown that the fatigue strength of welded steel structures does not depend on mechanical properties of the base steel (Duchet et al. [1]). With respect to conventional steel grades, the benefit of using advanced high strength steel grades is thus limited from the point of view of fatigue resistance. Nevertheless, there is some interest in using AHSS when Shot Peening (SP) is applied to the critical regions of welded assemblies. Indeed, once shot peening has been applied, AHSS grades offer better fatigue resistance in comparison with conventional steel grades. The local reinforcement of welds by shot peening therefore seems to be an efficient technique, compatible with industry requirements and cost-effective (Duchet et al. [2]) to improve the fatigue resistance.

According to Wohlfahrt [3], the effect of shot peening on the fatigue strength can be attributed to the changes of the residual stress state, work hardening state, surface roughness and the possible phase transformations. Though the benefit effect of SP on the fatigue strength of welded structures is largely reported in different studies (Hensel et al. [4], Haagensen and Maddox [5]), the respective roles of residual stresses, work hardening and surface roughness remain unclear. In the past, some

¹ LAMPA, Arts et Métiers, Sciences et Technologies, 49035 Angers, Cedex, France

² IRT M2P, 57070 Metz, France

³ ArcelorMittal Maizières Research SAS, 57283 Maizières-lès-Metz Cedex, France

⁴ Stellantis (ex-Groupe PSA), Chassis System Engineering, 25420 Voujeaucourt, France

studies have been conducted to investigate the individual effects of residual stresses and work hardening on the fatigue strength of peened welds (Lefebvre et al. [6], Sakino et al. [7] and Schubnell et al [8]). Lefebvre et al. [6] and Sakino et al. [7] investigated the effect of compressive residual stresses by comparing peened joints and heat-treated (HT) ones. They concluded that residual stresses are solely responsible for the improvement of fatigue strength. However, all these studies were performed on joints with thickness of 9-20 mm. Yamaguchi et al. [9] showed that compressive residual stresses and work hardening make comparable contributions to the increase in the fatigue strength of lap joints with thickness of 2.9 mm. However, this investigation was performed with bending fatigue tests and using micro-needle peening as the local reinforcement technique. Only limited experimental data regarding the uniaxial fatigue behaviour of as-welded and shot-peened structures made with AHSS is available.

The first aim of this work is to assess the potential effect of shot peening on the fatigue strength of GMAW double lap joints made of AHSS with a thickness of 3.8 mm. For this purpose, uniaxial fatigue tests were performed, and the effect of the load ratio was investigated. Furthermore, the features of SP treated joints, including residual stress, work hardening and surface roughness were also evaluated and compared with those of as-welded specimens. The second objective of this work is to separate the contributions of residual stresses, work hardening and surface roughness induced by SP on the fatigue strength. To this aim, the fatigue strengths of shot-peened welded assemblies, which were either heat-treated and/or preloaded (PL), were compared.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Material and specimen preparation

The material used in this study is a ferrite-bainite FB600 AHSS (HDT580F according to EN 10338) with a thickness of 3.8 mm. The mechanical properties obtained from monotonic tensile tests are presented in table 1. Double lap welded joints were prepared using the welding conditions shown in table 2. The double lap geometry is symmetric with respect to the loading axis and hence limits the effect of secondary bending stresses. A clamping device was used to reduce welding distortion. Welding was carried out by the Gas Metal Arc Welding (GMAW) process, with the G4Si1 filler material. The cut-outs are made in such a way that the rolling direction is aligned with the loading direction. The specimen geometry is shown in figure 1.a. Despite the clamping device, after welding the specimens exhibit an average angular distortion of 0.6° (figure 1.b).

Shot peening was performed with a compressed air jet machine on the two weld toes (figure 1.c). The angle between the direction of the shot and the vertical surface of the base steel coupon was set at 60° , with a working distance of 180 mm. The Almen intensity of the shot peening process was 21 A, with 200% coverage. The peening media was cut wire with a size of 400 μm .

TABLE 1 Mechanical properties of base metal FB600 (in the rolling direction)

Yield strength (MPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation (%)
495	590	20.5

TABLE 2 Welding conditions

Current (A)	Voltage (V)	Speed (mm/min)	Gas	Gas flow rate (L/min)
249	24.8	400	8% CO ₂ +92% Ar	18

FIGURE 1 (a) Specimen nominal geometry (units in mm), (b) Specimen geometry with angular welding distortion, (c) Shot peening apparatus

Test configurations

To investigate the effect of shot peening as well as to separate the contributions of residual stresses, work hardening and weld geometry on the fatigue strength of double lap joints, six different configurations were considered:

- As-welded (AW): specimens were welded in conditions shown in table 2.
- Shot-peened (SP): specimens were welded and shot-peened using the above conditions. The effect of SP can be verified by comparing the fatigue test results for AW joints and SP ones.
- Preloaded, then shot peened (PL-SP): specimens were welded, preloaded and then shot-peened. The aim of the preload is to reduce the angular distortion induced by the welding process. The preload consists of applying a uniaxial tensile nominal stress that corresponds to 110% of the yield strength (YS) of the base metal.
- Shot peened, then pre-loaded (SP-PL): specimens were welded, shot-peened and then preloaded (tension up to 110% of YS). The objectives of this preload are to reduce distortion, and to relieve residual stresses induced by SP, while preserving the work hardening introduced by the process. The effect of shot-peening-induced residual stresses can be evaluated by comparing the fatigue test results for the PL-SP specimens and the SP-PL specimens.
- Pre-loaded, shot peened and then heat-treated (PL-SP-HT): specimens were welded, preloaded, shot-peened and annealed. The annealing consisted of holding specimens at 550°C for 2.5 hours. This heat treatment was selected to relieve the residual stresses and reduce the work hardening

induced by SP. The effect of work hardening can therefore be investigated by comparing the fatigue test results for the PL-SP-HT joints and SP-PL joints.

- As-welded and pre-loaded (AW-PL): specimens were welded and preloaded (tension up to 110% of YS). The effect of SP surface roughness change caused by SP can be estimated by comparing the fatigue test results for the PL-SP-HT specimens and the AW-PL specimens.

Topography characterisation

The surface roughness was measured at the vicinity of the weld toe using a Bruker optical scanning profilometer. To evaluate the weld toe topography, the specimens were tilted at an angle of 45° with respect to the horizontal direction. Measurements were carried out along the loading direction over a length of 500 µm. For a given specimen, both the Ra and Rz values were evaluated for twenty measurement lines after application of filters $\lambda_c = 250 \mu\text{m}$ and $\lambda_s = 2.5 \mu\text{m}$.

Residual stresses and work hardening analysis

Residual stresses were analysed using X-ray diffraction techniques (Noyan and Cohen [10]). Specifically, a monochromatic beam of X-rays was produced by a chromium anode. The corresponding penetration depth is about 5 µm. The irradiated area, which was located at the weld toe, was delimited with a collimator of diameter 0.5 mm. X-ray diffraction patterns were collected with a linear detector. The 2θ range was adjusted to obtain the positions of the diffraction peaks of {211} lattices planes for different scattering directions. These positions were then used to evaluate the transversal σ_t and longitudinal σ_l residual stresses according to the $\sin^2\psi$ method. Also, the residual hydrostatic pressure σ_h , was evaluated according to equation 1.

$$\sigma_h = \frac{1}{3}(\sigma_t + \sigma_l) \quad (1)$$

To determine the in-depth distribution of residual stresses at the weld toe, successive material removal operations and X-ray diffraction analyses were performed. Material was removed using an electro-polishing process. To evaluate whether cyclic plasticity causes stress relaxation or not, some X-ray diffraction analyses were carried out on shot-peened specimens both before and after cyclic loading. To evaluate work hardening, the full width at half-maximum (FWHM) of the X-ray diffraction peaks was estimated. The FWHM provides a qualitative measure of work hardening.

Fatigue tests

Uniaxial fatigue tests were conducted using a servo-hydraulic machine under load control. The tests were carried out with a frequency of 10 Hz and a load ratio of either $R = 0.1$ or -1 . A number of cycles of 2×10^6 was used as the runout condition.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Roughness and distortion

Figure 2 shows the results of surface topography measurements of a weld toe prior to and after shot peening. The weld toe of the “as-welded (AW)” specimen is covered by defects such as weld ripples, weld spatter and welding undercuts. After shot peening, both the ripples and spatter were eliminated.

The results of surface roughness measurements are presented in table 3. Shot peening increased the roughness compared to the “as-welded” specimen. Such geometrical effects of shot peening are largely reported in the literature (e.g. Ahola et al. [11]).

FIGURE 2 Surface topography of weld toes (with respect to a mean profile line): (a) AW, (b) SP

TABLE 3 Results of roughness measurements

Configurations	Ra (μm)	Rz (μm)
AW	22 ± 7	167 ± 51
SP	36 ± 10	227 ± 54

The average angular distortion is presented for the different configurations in figure 3. The application of a preload significantly decreased the angular distortion induced by the welding process. The reduction of the geometrical distortion limits the contribution of the bending moment to the stress field. This contribution, which vanishes for perfectly flat specimens, is caused by clamping of the specimen.

FIGURE 3 Angular distortion of different configurations with standard deviations

Residual stresses

The initial (i.e., before fatigue loading) in-depth distribution of the residual hydrostatic stress is presented in figure 4.a from the free surface to a depth of 600 μm . Before shot peening, a compressive residual stress of ≈ -100 MPa is observed near the free surface of “as-welded (AW)” specimen. Shot peening (SP) generates compressive residual stresses up to a depth of ≈ 500 μm . The surface value is about ≈ -200 MPa. The maximum compressive stress is about ≈ -250 MPa located at depth of ≈ 100 μm . Both the preload and the heat treatment, when applied after shot peening, relieve the residual stresses induced by shot peening. For the “shot-peened and preloaded (SP-PL)” specimen, the surface value is ≈ -100 MPa, as in the case of “as-welded” specimen. After welding and preloading (AW-PL), the surface residual hydrostatic stress is reduced to ≈ -50 MPa. For the “preloaded and shot-peened (PL-SP)” specimen, the compressive residual stress at the surface is similar to that of the “shot-peened (SP)” specimen.

FIGURE 4 X-ray diffraction results for different specimen configurations: (a) residual stresses distribution; (b) FWHM distribution

The effect of a cyclic loading on the redistribution of transverse residual stresses is presented in figure 5 for different maximum nominal stresses and load ratios. At $R = -1$, a slight relaxation of compressive residual stresses is observed at the weld toe (≈ -38 MPa for $\sigma_{\text{max}} = 170$ MPa and ≈ -55 MPa for $\sigma_{\text{max}} = 220$ MPa). At $R = 0.1$, no residual stress relaxation was observed at $\sigma_{\text{max}} = 222$ MPa, which corresponds to the endurance limit. However, at $\sigma_{\text{max}} = 356$ MPa, the surface residual stress is reduced to -93 MPa, which indicates that significant plastic deformation took place at the weld toe during the fatigue tests.

FIGURE 5 Evolution of transverse residual stresses after $N = 10^4$ cycles: (a) $R = -1$, (b) $R = 0.1$

Work hardening

Figure 4.b shows the distribution of the average FWHM of X-ray diffraction peaks. Firstly, the “shot-peened” specimen displays the highest work hardening. The depth affected by shot peening is about $\approx 500 \mu\text{m}$, as per the residual stresses. Secondly, the heat treatment eliminates the work hardening introduced by the SP process. Specifically, after heat treatment, the FWHM is similar to that of the “as-welded” specimen. Finally, the preloaded “shot-peened” configurations preserves a part of the work hardening introduced by SP. It is worth mentioning that the geometries of the weld toe are not identical for different specimens. As a result, the differences between the “shot-peened (SP)” and “shot-peened and preloaded (SP-PL)” specimens are possible consequences of the dispersion of the welding and shot peening processes.

Fatigue strength at $R = -1$ and $R = 0.1$

Figure 6 shows the SN curves of “as-welded (AW)” specimens and “shot-peened (SP)” ones at load ratios of $R = -1$ and $R = 0.1$. The Basquin curves corresponding to a 50% probability of failure are also plotted.

Firstly, shot peening significantly improves the fatigue strength of double lap welded joints, particularly in tension-compression. Indeed, at $R = -1$, the fatigue strength at 10^6 cycles of the “shot-peened” specimens is about 140% higher than that of the “as-welded” specimens. The fatigue-strength improvement at $R = 0.1$ is less than that at $R = -1$, particularly for the low cycle regime. At $N = 10^6$ cycles, the fatigue strength of “shot-peened” joints is $\approx 50\%$ higher than that of “as-welded” joints. At $N = 10^5$ cycles, the fatigue strength of the “shot-peened” joints is only $\approx 15\%$ higher than that of the “as-welded” specimens.

The experimental data also indicates that the fatigue resistance of the “shot-peened” specimens depends on the load ratio. Such results are consistent with previous work by (Hensel [12] and Okawa et al. [13]). Figure 6 also illustrates that, for “as-welded” joints, the loading ratio has no significant influence on the fatigue strength, especially at $N = 10^6$ cycles.

FIGURE 6 SN curves of as-welded (AW) and shot-peened (SP) joints at R = -1 and R = 0.1

Effects of residual stress, work hardening and surface topography on the fatigue strength of SP joints

The SN curves of AW, SP, SP-PL, PL-SP, PL-SP-HT and AW-PL specimens at R = 0.1 are presented in figure 7. Firstly, in comparison with the “shot-peened” specimens, the application of a preload after shot peening strongly decreases the fatigue strength of the “preloaded and shot-peened” specimens. At $N = 3 \times 10^5$ cycles, the fatigue strength of the “shot-peened and preloaded (SP-PL)” joints is $\approx 22\%$ lower than that of the “preloaded and shot-peened (PL-SP)” joints. The difference is also prominent in the high cycle regime, the run-out stresses between the two configurations are different (300 MPa for PL-SP and 200 MPa for SP-PL). Secondly, there is no significant difference in the fatigue test results between the SP-PL and the PL-SP-HT specimens. Also, the results obtained for the PL-SP-HT and the AW-PL configurations are quite similar. Finally, when comparing the SP and the PL-SP configurations on the one hand and AW and the AW-PL configurations on the other, it can be seen that the fatigue strength is increased after preload, both in the low and high cycle regimes.

FIGURE 7 SN curves of AW, SP, AW-PL, SP-PL, PL-SP and PL-SP-HT joints (R = 0.1)

DISCUSSIONS

Effect of shot peening at R = -1 and R = 0.1

The fatigue test results for the “shot-peened (SP)” and the “as-welded (AW)” specimens show the beneficial effect of SP for both R = -1 and R = 0.1. However, the beneficial effect at R = 0.1 is limited, particularly in the low cycle regime. This lower benefit of shot peening for low number of cycles to failure is caused by the partial relaxation of the compressive residual stresses shown in figure 5. Indeed, the relaxation of compressive residual stresses after cyclic loading is more significant at R = 0.1 than R = -1. The relaxation of residual stresses is attributed to the local plastic deformation at the weld toe, which occurs when the effective stress (applied stress and residual stress) exceeds the local yield stress. Similar results were reported by Leguinagoicoa et al. [14]. The experimental results also indicate that the fatigue strength of the “as-welded” joints is not significantly influenced by the fatigue load ratio R. This can be explained by the existence of compressive residual stresses at the weld toe, due to cyclic plasticity confined at R = 0.1. The residual stresses reduce the local mean stress, thus it is closer to the observed value for R=-1. Similar results were reported by Hensel [12].

Major factor controlling the fatigue strength of SP joints

From the results obtained for the different configurations, it is possible to separate out the individual contributions of residual stresses, work hardening and surface roughness on the fatigue strength of double lap joints.

Firstly, the comparison of the fatigue strength of the “preloaded and shot-peened (PL-SP)” and the “shot-peened and preloaded (SP-PL)” joints shows a significant difference. This difference is more prominent in the high cycle regime. As shown above, these two configurations exhibit small and comparable angular distortion. The difference in terms of the FWHM is negligible ($\approx 8\%$ at surface). As a result, the difference in the fatigue strength between these two configurations should not be interpreted as a consequence of the decrease in the FWHM. Indeed, the empirical formula proposed by (Nakamura and Horikawa [15]) can be used to translate this decrease of FWHM between the surface of the SP-PL and the PL-SP joints to a fatigue strength (fatigue strength at 3×10^5 cycles) decrease of $\approx 5\%$. This value is much smaller than the actual decrease ($\approx 22\%$). Since the main difference between these two configurations is the residual stress state, the compressive residual stresses introduced by shot peening, which are relaxed when shot peening is followed by a preload, are the most prominent factors controlling the fatigue resistance. The effect is less pronounced in the low cycle regime because of the relaxation of residual stresses caused by cyclic plasticity, as previously shown in figure 5.

Second, there is no major difference in fatigue test results between the “shot-peened and preloaded (SP-PL)” specimens and the “preloaded shot-peened and heat-treated (PL-SP-HT)” specimens. As described above, these configurations have small and comparable welding distortion. The compressive residual stresses introduced by shot peening were almost fully relieved for both configurations. These residual stresses therefore have little effect on the fatigue strength. Additionally, no change of surface roughness is observed after the heat treatment. As a result, the comparison of fatigue test results between the SP-PL and the PL-SP-HT specimens should be interpreted as the effect of work hardening induced by SP. Using the above observations, one concludes that the role of work hardening on the fatigue strength is therefore negligible.

Finally, the comparison between the fatigue test results of the “as-welded and preloaded (AW-PL)” and the “preloaded shot-peened and heat-treated (PL-SP-HT)” configurations shows no major difference. For these two configurations, the distortions are small and the work hardening and residual stresses are comparable. The main difference between the two configurations is the surface roughness introduced by shot peening. Since the fatigue test results for these two configurations are similar, the effect of surface roughness is negligible. This small effect on fatigue behaviour can be explained by the competition between the elimination of weld defects and the increase of surface roughness after shot peening. Shiozaki et al. [16] and Schork et al. [17] reported that the weld ripples, as sources of microscopic stress concentration, affected the fatigue strength of welded joint.

The difference in fatigue strength between the “shot-peened (SP)” and the “preloaded and shot-peened (PL-SP)” on the one hand and “as-welded (AW)” and the “as-welded and preloaded (AW-PL)” on the other is mainly attributed to the beneficial effect of welding distortion correction, as previously shown in figure 3.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the potential effects of shot peening on the fatigue strength of welded double lap joints made of Advanced High Strength Steel FB600 (thickness of 3.8 mm) under two loading ratios were investigated. The major factor controlling the fatigue strength of shot-peened welded joints was found by comparing the fatigue strength, residual stresses, work hardening and surface roughness of shot-peened welded joints, which were either heat-treated and/or preloaded. The principal conclusions of this work are:

- 1) Shot peening introduces compressive residual stresses and generates work hardening up to a depth of around 500 μm .
- 2) Shot peening improves the fatigue strength of lap welded joints. The improvement however decreases with an increasing load ratio.
- 3) Residual stress redistribution caused by cyclic loading is more important at $R = 0.1$ than $R = -1$.
- 4) The existence of compressive residual stresses is the major factor that governs the fatigue strength. Work hardening and surface roughness seem to have a little effect on fatigue strength.

Further work will focus on the evaluation of both the crack initiation and crack propagation stages. At the end, a fatigue design strategy will be proposed to account for the beneficial effects of shot peening on the fatigue strength of FB600 welded lap joints.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The research is supported by IRT M2P institute, ArcelorMittal company and Stellantis company within the “SGN project”.

REFERENCE LIST

- (1) Duchet, M., Amblard, M., Cretteur, L., Michaut, S., Goudemez, J., Weber, B., Brière, O., and Desfontaine, V., Fatigue behaviour of arc welded assemblies: paths of improvement, in: Senlis - France, 2011.
- (2) Duchet, M., Haouas, J., Gibeau, E., Pechenot, F., Honecker, C., Munier, R., and Weber, B., Improvement of the fatigue strength of welds for lightweight chassis application made of Advanced High Strength Steels, *Procedia Struct. Integr.* 19 (2019) 585–594.
- (3) Wohlfahrt, H., The influence of peening conditions on the resulting distribution of residual stress, in: *Proc. Second Int. Conf. Shot Peen.*, Chicago, 1984: pp. 316–331.
- (4) Hensel, J., Eslami, H., Nitschke-Pagel, T., and Dilger, K., Fatigue Strength Enhancement of Butt Welds by Means of Shot Peening and Clean Blasting, (2019) 9.
- (5) Maddox, S., Improving the fatigue strength of welded joints by peening, *Met. Constr.* 17 (1985) 220–224.
- (6) Lefebvre, F., Peyrac, C., Elbel, G., Revilla-Gomez, C., Verdu, C., and Buffière, J.-Y., Understanding of fatigue strength improvement of steel structures by hammer peening treatment, *Procedia Eng.* 133 (2015) 454–464.
- (7) Sakino, Y., Sano, Y., Sumiya, R., and Kim, Y.-C., Major factor causing improvement in fatigue strength of butt welded steel joints after laser peening without coating, *Sci. Technol. Weld. Join.* 17 (2012) 402–407.
- (8) Schubnell, J., Pontner, P., Wimpory, R., Farajian, M., and Schulze, V., The influence of work hardening and residual stresses on the fatigue behavior of high frequency mechanical impact treated surface layers, *Int. J. Fatigue.* 134 (2020) 105450.

- (9) Yamaguchi, N., Shiozaki, T., and Tamai, Y., Micro-needle peening method to improve fatigue strength of arc-welded ultra-high strength steel joints, *J. Mater. Process. Technol.* 288 (2021) 116894.
- (10) Noyan, I.C. and Cohen, J.B., *Residual stress: measurement by diffraction and interpretation*, Springer, 2013.
- (11) Ahola, A., Lipiäinen, K., Riski, J., Koskimäki, M., Pyörret, J., and Björk, T., Fatigue strength of shot-peened as-welded joints and post-weld-treated and subsequently clean-blasted fillet weld joints, *Weld. World.* (2023) 1–16.
- (12) Hensel, J., Mean stress correction in fatigue design under consideration of welding residual stress, *Weld. World.* 64 (2020) 535–544.
- (13) Okawa, T., Shimanuki, H., Funatsu, Y., Nose, T., and Sumi, Y., Effect of preload and stress ratio on fatigue strength of welded joints improved by ultrasonic impact treatment, *Weld. World.* 57 (2013) 235–241.
- (14) Leguinaigoicoa, N., Albizuri, J., and Larranaga, A., Fatigue improvement and residual stress relaxation of shot-peened alloy steel DIN 34CrNiMo6 under axial loading, *Int. J. Fatigue.* 162 (2022) 107006.
- (15) Nakamura, H. and Horikawa, T., *Fatigue strength of metal and application to fatigue strength design*, (2008).
- (16) Shiozaki, T., Yamaguchi, N., Tamai, Y., Hiramoto, J., and Ogawa, K., Effect of weld toe geometry on fatigue life of lap fillet welded ultra-high strength steel joints, *Int. J. Fatigue.* 116 (2018) 409–420.
- (17) Schork, B., Kucharczyk, P., Madia, M., Zerbst, U., Hensel, J., Bernhard, J., Tchuindjang, D., Kaffenberger, M., and Oechsner, M., The effect of the local and global weld geometry as well as material defects on crack initiation and fatigue strength, *Eng. Fract. Mech.* 198 (2018) 103–122.